

A Use Case Analysis for Identity Management in Industrial Systems

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Abstract—As industrial systems increasingly integrate Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT), the need for robust identity management solutions becomes critical to ensure the security and integrity of these complex environments. Traditional approaches to identity management are often unable to address the unique challenges of industrial systems, which require secure and reliable methods for managing multiple identities across different devices, applications and networks. This paper presents a novel approach for improved identity management by integrating blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) into industrial systems. By leveraging the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain technology, SSI provides a secure, scalable and tamper-proof solution for managing identities in industrial contexts. Several use cases are discussed that illustrate the practical application of blockchain-based SSI in securing cell/area zones, administrative users, infrastructure services, plant-wide applications, and other critical aspects of industrial systems. Through these discussions, the paper shows how blockchain-based SSI can significantly improve identity management by ensuring that all entities within an industrial network are authenticated, authorized, and protected against a variety of cyber threats.

Index Terms—SSI, Blockchain, industrial networks, 6G

I. INTRODUCTION

In today’s rapidly evolving industrial landscape, securing Industrial Automated Control System (IACS) has become increasingly complex [1]. Traditional approaches to identity management are often inadequate to address the unique challenges of industrial environments characterized by multiple legacy systems, Operational Technologies (OTs) and stringent security requirements. As industrial systems become increasingly connected and digitized, the need for robust, scalable and secure identity management solutions is paramount [2]. Protecting IACS from cyber threats is a major concern for organizations. However, it can be challenging to translate these concerns into actionable strategies, especially when it comes to the complexity of legacy systems and outdated security practices. The introduction of blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) provides a transformative approach to managing identity and access control in these environments [3], [4], ensuring that only verified entities can interact with critical infrastructure. Previous research has been developed specifically for industrial applications [5], and in this paper we integrate state-of-the-art blockchain-based SSI solutions. This approach enables the secure and decentralized management of identities and ensures

that all interactions within the IACS environment are authenticated and traceable.

The industrial security architecture of this paper, complemented by blockchain-based SSI, simplifies the complexity of networks by focusing on securing use cases through verifiable identities. This model comprehensively addresses each use case and addresses today’s cyber threats while leveraging SSI to ensure that only authenticated entities can access the operational network. A novel approach is used to improve identity management in industrial systems by integrating blockchain-based SSI into existing security architectures. By leveraging the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain, we provide a more secure and flexible way to manage identities in various industrial applications through several use cases. The integration of SSI not only strengthens access control mechanisms, but also ensures that all entities interacting with industrial systems are verifiable and trustworthy.

In this paper, we explore the logical framework and reference architectures that support the integration of blockchain-based SSI into industrial systems. In addition, we look at various common use cases such as securing cells/areas, managing users and locking Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) through the usage of blockchain-based SSI. Finally, we provide recommendations for overcoming security challenges and conclude with the implications of this approach for the future of industrial cybersecurity. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive guide for industrial organizations looking to improve their identity management systems to ensure their operations remain secure, resilient and meet industry standards.

II. BACKGROUND, THREATS FOR INDUSTRIAL SYSTEMS

A. Threats in Industrial environments

Various threats in industrial environments could be exploited by external threat actors. Figure 1 provides a comprehensive overview of threats in industrial environments. It begins at the top with a depiction of external threat actors, which could include hackers or other malicious entities attempting to penetrate the industrial system. These threat actors attempt to penetrate the network by exploiting vulnerabilities such as weak separation between endpoints and other systems, even if they are protected by firewalls. As we move deeper into the industrial environment, the diagram shows further risks in the

III. COMMON USE CASES

IT/OT convergence layer, such as outdated software on systems like control room workstations. These outdated systems often lack the latest security patches, making them a prime target for attacks such as Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS). The diagram also shows the lack of segmentation in network design, which allows an attacker to move laterally across systems and compromise various devices such as Human-Machine Interfaces (HMIs), PLCs and other critical infrastructure components.

Another significant risk is the presence of forgotten devices on the network, such as older PLCs, which may no longer be actively managed or monitored. If left unprotected, these devices could serve as a gateway for attackers to gain unauthorized access to the industrial control system. To mitigate these vulnerabilities, integrating blockchain-based SSI into the industrial environment can provide a robust solution. Blockchain-based SSI ensures that all entities within the network, whether users, devices or software applications, are authenticated through a decentralized and immutable identity verification process. By implementing SSI, organizations can enforce strong, cryptographically secured password policies, eliminate the need for written passwords through passwordless authentication, and ensure that only verified and authorized devices and users can interact with critical systems. In addition, blockchain-based SSI can improve network segmentation by providing identity-based access controls that prevent unauthorized lateral movement within the network. This would also make forgotten devices and outdated software less of a security threat, as these systems would require valid, up-to-date credentials for each operation within the network. In summary, the integration of blockchain-based SSI into this industrial environment would significantly reduce the risk of these presented threats and create a more secure and resilient infrastructure against external threats.

B. Segmenting IT & OT Networks

The first step in securing industrial networks is to restrict logical access to the OT network. By implementing a blockchain-based SSI within an Industrial Demilitarized Zone (IDMZ), companies can ensure that all interactions between corporate and OT networks are authenticated and secure. This approach prevents unauthorized access and mitigates the impact of potential security incidents. With the growing demand for Industrial IoT (IIoT) and the convergence of IT/OT/cloud, the need for a scalable and consistent security strategy is becoming increasingly important. A hybrid cloud-IDMZ model enhanced with blockchain-based SSI provides a repeatable and consistent architecture. This approach supports a regional operations center model that enables organizations with a global footprint to maintain consistent security policies across multiple locations. Securing the hardware is fundamental to the overall security of the network. Blockchain-based SSI complements the security of the hardware by ensuring that all interactions with the hardware are authenticated and traceable. Compliance with standards such as IEC62443-4-1, which focuses on the secure development of IACS products, is essential for a secure-by-design approach.

Understanding the techniques used to infiltrate industrial networks is critical to effective defense. Resources such as the MITRE ATT&CK for ICS framework [6] and the Verizon Data Breach Investigations Report (DBIR) provide valuable insights. Blockchain-based SSI adds another dimension to these strategies by ensuring that all interactions within the network are authenticated, making it more difficult for adversaries to gain unauthorized access. In industrial networks, different use cases and personas exist [7] and they need to be secured with blockchain-based SSI. For example, in the cell/area zone, SSI ensures that only verified devices communicate across zones to prevent unauthorized access and maintain network segmentation. Administrative users, infrastructure services and plantwide applications can all benefit from the added security of SSI by ensuring that their access is secure and traceable.

A. Use Case 1: Cell/Area Zone with SSI

The cell/area zone within an industrial network usually consists of several zones in which devices communicate freely with each other [8]. With the integration of blockchain-based SSI, all devices within a cell/area zone must authenticate their identity before they start communicating. This ensures that only verified devices can interact within the zone, providing an additional layer of security. Cross-zone communication remains restricted unless explicitly allowed, as shown in Figure 2.

Blockchain-based SSI enhances this facility by maintaining an immutable record of all authentication events, ensuring traceability and security within the cell/area zone. The network architecture in an industrial environment focuses on communication between two Cell/Area Zones (Zone-1 and Zone-2). A security posture is required where communication between these zones is denied by default, which corresponds to a "deny all" approach for cross-zone traffic. This approach is a fundamental aspect of securing OT (Operational Technology) networks and ensures that no unauthorized data or commands can be transmitted between critical areas within the industrial process. Each cell/area zone includes critical components such as human-machine interfaces (HMIs), programmable logic controllers (PLCs), remote terminal units (RTUs) and other industrial devices. These zones are connected to network switches that manage internal communication between devices within the same zone. Despite this internal connectivity, the illustration highlights that there is no segmentation within the zone itself, meaning that while communication between zones is restricted, devices within the same zone can communicate freely with each other. An important aspect is the presence of a "deny" indicator between the distribution stacks of the two cell/area zones, which indicates that any attempt to communicate across zones will be blocked by default. This security measure is important to prevent lateral movement of threats within the OT environment and to ensure that a breach in one zone does not compromise the entire network.

Fig. 1: Threats in industrial environments and blockchain-based SSI Mitigation.

Fig. 2: Cell/Area Zone to Cell/Area Zone communication is denied by default. Segmentation is enforced with SSI.

B. Use Case 2: Administrative Users with SSI

As shown in Figure 3, the administrative users often need access to all zones within the network for tasks such as network configuration and applying control logic [9]. With blockchain-based SSI, the identity of each administrative user is cryptographically verified before access is granted to ensure that only authorized personnel can modify critical network settings. This approach not only protects data, but also provides a tamper-proof audit trail for administrative actions, increasing security and accountability.

C. Use Case 3: Infrastructure Services with SSI

Infrastructure services such as DHCP, NTP or LDAP, require access to several areas of the system [10]. As shown in Figure 4, by integrating blockchain-based SSI, these services can authenticate and verify their identity across the network, ensuring that only legitimate services gain access to critical infrastructure. This reduces the risk of unauthorized interactions between services and provides a secure, decentralized method of managing service identities within the network.

D. Use Case 4: Plantwide Applications with SSI

As can be seen in Figure 5, industrial applications often require special access rights to interact with machines or monitor plant floor equipment [11]. With blockchain-based SSI, the identity of each application can be verified before access is granted to ensure that only authenticated applications can interact with the required systems. This limits access to only what is necessary, reducing the risk of unauthorized application activity and increasing overall security.

Finally, Table I provides a summary of the studied use cases for blockchain-based SSI in industrial networks.

IV. SECURITY CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The first major challenge is the lack of visibility of the IACS network. Industrial networks, which are often outdated and scattered, have difficulty maintaining an accurate inventory of connected devices. This lack of visibility hinders the ability to create a secure communication architecture. Blockchain-based SSI can remedy this by providing a decentralized and immutable record of all devices and interactions within the network, improving visibility and control. Without adequate visibility, segmentation and control are almost impossible. OT networks, often deployed with minimal or no security policies, are vulnerable to attack. Blockchain-based SSI can enable more effective segmentation by ensuring that only verified devices and users can access specific network segments, preventing unauthorized access and potential breaches. This is crucial, as poor segmentation can have serious consequences, including production disruption, loss of revenue and even security risks. Secondly, the threat of malware in industrial environments requires a robust security strategy. Malware must be prevented, detected and contained to limit the potential damage. Blockchain-based SSI provides an additional layer of protection by ensuring that only authenticated entities can

execute commands within the network, reducing the risk of malware spreading.

Finally, Operational Technology (OT) teams with their expertise in devices, protocols and processes need to work with Information Technology (IT) teams that understand the network infrastructure. Security teams focused on identifying and mitigating threats must now consider the role of SSI in improving security. Together, these teams can leverage existing network and SSI technologies to protect industrial systems and ensure continuous production without compromising security or uptime. The proposed solution, enhanced with blockchain-based SSI, can be used by IT, OT and security teams together with their system integrators. Operations teams may find that the SSI integration enables seamless identity management and access control and supports a variety of IACS vendors and protocols. IT network managers will appreciate how SSI can be integrated with existing technologies to improve security in production environments. Security teams will gain better visibility into industrial assets and security events, with context enriched by SSI to ensure that only authenticated entities can interact with critical systems.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Implementation Setup

This paper presents the results of a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed architecture with programmatic event-driven simulations. The experiments of this section demonstrate the benefits of integrating blockchain for SSI in industrial automation architecture. We simulated the decentralized computing infrastructure of the Enterprise Zone, the IDMZ, the Industrial Site Operations Zone and the Cell/Area Zone with four virtual machines and one host machine. Aligning to the micro-services architecture, which is widely used in industry-grade systems, we implemented and deployed the services in Docker containers. Furthermore, we used virtual machines to run on Ubuntu 18.10 64-bit with 4 GB RAM and a single core allocation. The host machine has an Intel(R) Core i5 -8250 CPU with four cores and eight logical processors. The Hyperledger Fabric blockchain is deployed on virtual machines with REST Application Programming Interface (API) connectivity to simulate the SSI service in the proposed architecture. We first initialized the system with pre-registered entities to simulate the SSI integration scenarios in the Industrial Site Operations Zone. In this experiment, we used two multi-threaded software programs to create DoS attacks and legitimate traffic as indicated in Figure 6. In addition, we evaluated the end-to-end latency of single and batched transaction completion using time-stamping programming libraries.

B. Robustness of the IT and OT to the DoS attacks

In this experiment, we evaluated the robustness of IT and OT against simulated DDoS attacks. Specifically, we assumed that the latency of legitimate request processing will be affected by the DDoS attacks, compromising the service availability. After programmatic launching of the attacks, we compared latency

Fig. 3: Administrative users require access to all zones that are secured and verified with SSI.

Fig. 4: Infrastructure services require secure access to all Cell/Area Zones, facilitated by SSI.

Fig. 5: Applications require access to specific services in the cell, secured with SSI.

TABLE I: Blockchain-based SSI Use Cases in Industrial Networks

Use Case	Pros with Blockchain Systems	Cons with Blockchain Systems	Additional Considerations	Addressing Drawbacks
Cell/Area Zone [7], [8]	Immutable, decentralized record of device interactions. Enhanced network segmentation, reducing lateral threats.	Complexity in integrating with legacy OT systems. May increase initial deployment costs.	Enhances real-time security for mission-critical devices, such as PLCs and sensors.	Use SSI gateways or middleware to simplify integration with legacy systems.
Administrative Users [9]	Cryptographically secure identity verification. Tamper-proof audit trails increase accountability.	Managing cryptographic keys adds complexity. Resistance to adoption from administrative staff.	Ensures network settings are protected from unauthorized changes, improving overall security.	Implement user-friendly key management tools and provide training to overcome adoption hurdles.
Infrastructure Services [10]	Ensures only legitimate services like DHCP and LDAP access critical infrastructure. Eliminates service impersonation.	Potential service latency during authentication. Higher computational resource usage for validation.	Protects critical infrastructure by preventing rogue services from accessing sensitive areas.	Use lightweight cryptographic mechanisms to reduce latency while preserving security.
Plantwide Applications [11]	Only authenticated applications can interact with devices. Reduces risk of unauthorized app activity.	Integration complexity with legacy plant systems. High cost of reconfiguring applications.	Reliable for critical industrial applications such as ERP and MES, securing key operational processes.	Gradual migration of legacy systems, starting with the most critical applications.

with and without SSI integration while running malicious traffic scenarios for IT and OT service invocation. Figure 7 shows the degradation of legitimate requests with and without SSI verification for different *BatchTimeOut* configurations on blockchain-based SSI. The experiment was conducted with 500 ms, 1000 ms and 2000 ms block mining *BatchTimeOut* configurations of SSI. The malicious access requests to the IT and OT systems that led to DoS attacks were generated by the multithreaded program running on VM. In our experiments, we

gradually increased the attack traffic from 0 to 50 and evaluated the latency for calling the IT and OT services. Based on the results, we can clearly see that the end-to-end latency from the perspective of legitimate nodes increases as the number of malicious access requests increases in the system without SSI. This increase in latency indicates service outages due to flooded malicious requests, which affect service availability. In contrast, the experiment with the integrated SSI shows that the latency is not drastically affected by the malicious requests filtered by the

Fig. 6: Implementation setup

SSI. We observed that for 50 malicious transactions, the average latency of the legitimate transaction on a system without SSI is 119 seconds. In contrast, the average latency is significantly lower (up to 5 seconds) when the SSI is integrated with the SSI because the malicious traffic has been filtered out.

C. Discussion

The experimental results demonstrate that our work is well-suited for a production-grade deployment by design. The API-based integration points especially ensure flexibility for seamless integration with existing systems. The smart contract-based operation of the APIs and associated functions guarantee the services are not maliciously modifiable, thereby securing against the identified challenges.

The experimental results clearly reflect the robustness of the IT and OT to DoS attacks. As the experiments were conducted in different scaled scenarios, the scalability features are well-indicated. The minimal impact on the legitimate request processing latency while attacks are present is the key indicator of our work that preserves the availability of the services. However, as indicated in Figure 7, the additional layer of blockchain is a tradeoff, up to 10 malicious messages per legitimate request. The tradeoff is eliminated when the number of malicious requests are increased.

VI. CONCLUSION

The integration of blockchain-based SSI into industrial systems represents a significant advance in the field of identity management. This approach addresses the complex security challenges associated with the convergence of IT and OT and provides a decentralized and tamper-proof solution that enhances the protection of industrial environments. The paper has shown how SSI can be effectively integrated into existing industrial automation architectures to provide robust, multi-layered endpoint protection and ensure secure identity management for various use cases. The practical application of blockchain-based SSI, as illustrated in the use cases discussed, highlights its potential to secure critical aspects of

Fig. 7: Robustness of the IT and OT to the DoS attacks

industrial systems, from cell/area zones to remote user access. As industrial systems continue to evolve and face increasingly sophisticated cyber threats, the adoption of blockchain-based SSI will be essential in maintaining the integrity, security, and resilience of these critical infrastructures. This novel approach provides a comprehensive framework for enhanced identity management, paving the way for more secure and reliable industrial systems in the future.

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